

Fabrication of a new Pr³⁺ nanocomposite carbon paste electrode based on bis(salicylaldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone as a material sensing

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Abstract : The fabrication and electrochemical behavior of nanocomposite CP-electrode modified with MWCNT/nanosilica was investigated for bis(salicylaldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (STCH) as a new ionophore in the presence of various alkaline, lanthanide and transition metal ions. Pursuant obtained results the best electrode behavior was belonged to Pr³⁺-carbon paste electrode (PrCPE) with composition of STCH : 3%, binder (paraffin oil) : 30%, modifier (MWCNT : 2%, NS : 0.3%), and graphite powder : 64.7%. This PrCPE displayed a Nernstian response by the slope of 19.6 ± 0.2 mV decade⁻¹ in linear range 1.0×10^{-8} to 1.0×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹ with a lower detection limit 8.5×10^{-9} mol L⁻¹. The pH range of this new praseodymium sensor was gained 2.1 to 8.9 with a response time about 6 s. To assessment the response of new prepared electrode toward different cations the matched potential method (K^{MPM}) was applied. Obtained results show good selectivity for this PrCPE with respect to a number of lanthanide and transition metal ions. It was successfully used as an indicator electrode in potentiometric titration of Pr³⁺ ions with EDTA and determination of Pr³⁺ content in several blends of ions.

Keywords : Praseodymium, ion selective electrode, bis(salicylaldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone, nanocomposite carbon paste electrode, potentiometry sensor.

Introduction

Potentiometric techniques based on ion selective electrodes are regularly used as acceptable analytical method between several methods which have been employed to determine the praseodymium ion in aqueous solutions¹⁻⁷. In the meantime, the carbon paste electrodes (CPEs) are one of the subgroup of ion selective sensors which tender renewable surface, stable response, and low ohmic resistance electrodes⁸⁻¹⁰.

Among the lanthanide series praseodymium is the second element with atomic number 59. It has a several implementations in various fields such as use in color TV, glasses, and fluorescent lamps. It is also used to add in fiber optic cables as a doping agent. Praseodymium could be entered in environment and gradually accumulate in soils and water by many various sources such as petrol-producing industries, throwing away the household equipment, etc. which cause to augment the concentrations of Pr³⁺ in humans body, animals and soil particles¹¹.

Lately, some ISEs for lanthanide ions such as praseodymium were reported by us and other researchers¹²⁻⁵⁸. In the present work, nanocomposite-CP based on bis(salicylaldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (STCH) (Fig. 1) as the active material, NS (nanosilica), MWCNTs (multi-walled carbon nanotubes) and paraffin oil has been developed to applied for monitoring of Pr³⁺ ion.

Fig. 1. Structure of STCH.

Experimental

EMF measurements :

A potentiometric cell involving the Pr³⁺-CP sensor as indicating electrode, an Ag/AgCl electrode purchased

from Azar electrode, Iran Co. as a reference electrode which both electrodes connected to a mili-voltmeter was employed to electromotive force measurement. All measurement was carried out with the CP-sensor using the following cell assembly :

CP-electrode | 1.0×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ Pr(NO₃)₃ | Ag/AgCl-KCl (satd.)

Chemicals and reagents :

The nano materials (nanosilica (NS), and multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) with 10–40 nm diameters, 1–25 μ m length) with 95% purity were purchased from Research Institute of the Petroleum Industry (Iran), the Merck Chemical and the Aldrich Co. were the suppliers for the nitrate and chloride salts of all cations, bis(salicylaldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (STCH), high-purity paraffin oil graphite powder (1–2 μ m particle size). Doubly distilled de-ionized water was used throughout.

Carbon paste electrode preparation :

Proceeding to prepare the CPE : First of all, the paste composition including paraffin oil (binder), STCH (ionophore), MWCNTs and NS (modifier), and graphite powder (inert matrix) were entirely mixed about 30–40 min to get homogenization paste. Next, the obtained paste was carefully and thoroughly packed up to the tip of a tube containing a copper wire which played the role as the electrical contact. Then, the surface of CPE was polished with soft paper to replace the external layer of the

carbon paste by the new smoothed one. Finally, the electrode was soaked in a 1.0×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ Pr(NO₃)₃ solutions for 48 h.

Results and discussion

Potential response of the electrode :

The Nernstian response of new designed electrode was studied by employing STCH as a sensing element to prepare of several lanthanide and some of other cations electrodes by potentiometric method. According to final results, among all other cations, praseodymium ion shows the best Nernstian response (Fig. 2).

Optimization of the PrCPE :

Different compositions of carbon paste based on the STCH were tested to determine Pr^{III} ion concentration and the results were listed in Table 1. The ion carrier is one of the main ingredients of any ISE, so the variety amount of STCH was used to fabricate a series of nano-composite CPEs to test the selectivity of it. Another component which causes to improve the behavior of the CPE such as conductivity of the sensor, increases the transduction of the chemical signal to electrical signal, and develops the dynamic working range is MWCNT. Two more ingredients of CPE are known as binder (here paraffin oil) and graphite powder as an inert matrix. Nanosilica is a filler compound with high specific surface area that enhances the mechanical properties of CP-electrode and helps to extraction of the ions into the surface of the CPE

Fig. 2. Potential responses of various ion-selective electrodes based on STCH.

Table 1. Optimization of the Pr³⁺-CPE ingredients

Electrode No.	Composition of carbon paste (wt.%)					Slope (mV/decade)	Dynamic linear range (M)
	Paraffin oil	Ligand	Graphite powder	MWCNTs	Nanosilicon		
1	25	3	69.5	2	0.5	21.9 ± 0.2	5.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
2	30	3	64.5	2	0.5	19.0 ± 0.3	5.0 × 10 ⁻⁷ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
3	35	3	59.5	2	0.5	16.1 ± 0.8	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
4	30	3	64.6	2	0.4	17.6 ± 0.3	5.0 × 10 ⁻⁷ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
5	30	3	64.7	2	0.3	19.6 ± 0.2	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁸ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
6	30	3	64.9	2	0.1	23.4 ± 0.3	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁷ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
7	30	3	63.7	3	0.3	16.2 ± 0.5	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁸ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
8	30	3	65.7	1	0.3	15.6 ± 0.6	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁷ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
9	30	2	65.7	2	0.3	16.6 ± 0.7	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
10	30	4	63.7	2	0.3	24.5 ± 0.4	5.0 × 10 ⁻⁸ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²

due to its hydrophobic property. In accordance to results the best response show by CPE No. 56 (0.3% NS, 2% MWCNT, 3% STCH, 30% paraffin oil and 64.7% graphite powder).

Calibration curve :

Based on optimization stage the best response of the Pr³⁺-CP-electrode based on STCH, illustrated in Fig. 3 as a calibration curve which put out the widish linear range from 1.0 × 10⁻⁸ to 1.0 × 10⁻² mol L⁻¹ and the slope of 19.6 ± 0.2 mV decade⁻¹ with lower detection limit of 8.5 × 10⁻⁹ mol L⁻¹ of praseodymium ions concentration⁵⁹⁻⁷².

Fig. 3. Calibration curves of the STCH based Pr³⁺-CP sensor.

pH influence :

The specified concentration of Pr³⁺ solution (1.0 × 10⁻³ M) was used over the pH 1.0–11.0 to study the effect of hydronium ions on the potential response of

Fig. 4. pH effect of 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ solution on the Pr³⁺ sensor based on STCH.

PrCPE. According to Fig. 4 there was no consequential change on the potential response over pH range of 2.1–8.9. The changes of potential at low pH values are attributed to the H₃O⁺ which is attributed to protonated ionophore in solution and the changes of potential at higher pH range is due to formation of some hydroxyl complexes of Pr³⁺ ions in solution⁷³⁻⁷⁹.

Dynamic response time of the PrCPE :

In order to assay the response time of ISE, several solutions was applied by measuring consecutively from the lower (1.0 × 10⁻⁸ mol L⁻¹) to the higher (1.0 × 10⁻² mol L⁻¹) concentration of the Pr³⁺ solution. Conforming to Fig. 5, the response time of PrCPE was ~6 s.

Selectivity studies of the PrCPE :

At this work the selectivity coefficients which indicate the priority of primary ion over interfering ions was measured graphically by the match potential method

Fig. 5. Dynamic response time of PrCPE based on STCH.

(MPM)⁸⁰⁻⁸³. In order to determine the selectivity coefficients, the potential of the specific activity of Pr³⁺ ions solution was measured, next, the amount of interfering ions solution was sequentially added to the same solution and the potential was read. In the last stage, the final results getting by the following equation that is the ratio of primary ion (A) activity changes to the interfering ion (B).

$$K_{ij}^{MPM} = \frac{\Delta S_A}{S_B}$$

Table 2 demonstrated the negligible disturbance of various cations for the PrCPE which indicates an acceptable performance of the designed CPE toward the Pr³⁺

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients ($K_{Pr^{3+}}^{MPM}$) of proposed Pr³⁺

sensor			
Interfering ion	K_{PrE}^{MPM}	Interfering ion	K_{PrE}^{MPM}
Lu ³⁺	5.0×10^{-3}	Yb ³⁺	6.0×10^{-4}
La ³⁺	8.0×10^{-3}	Mg ²⁺	8.5×10^{-5}
Tm ³⁺	1.0×10^{-4}	Pb ²⁺	2.2×10^{-4}
Nd ³⁺	9.0×10^{-3}	Na ⁺	4.0×10^{-5}
Eu ³⁺	4.5×10^{-5}	K ⁺	7.0×10^{-4}
Ho ³⁺	7.0×10^{-5}	Co ²⁺	1.0×10^{-5}
Gd ³⁺	1.0×10^{-4}	Cd ²⁺	6.0×10^{-4}
Sm ³⁺	9.0×10^{-5}	Ca ²⁺	6.0×10^{-5}
Er ³⁺	5.0×10^{-4}	Fe ³⁺	2.0×10^{-3}
Tb ³⁺	9.0×10^{-5}	Cr ³⁺	5.0×10^{-5}
Dy ³⁺	8.0×10^{-4}	Ni ²⁺	4.5×10^{-5}

ions and specific interaction between Pr³⁺ ions and STCH.

Analytical application :

To carry out potentiometric titration via the praseodymium CPE as an indicator electrode, 25 ml of 1.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ Pr^{III} was titrated by the certain amounts of 1.0×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹ EDTA. According to Fig. 6, this electrode can successfully determine the amount of praseodymium ions in solution.

Furthermore, it could put to use for scanning low level concentrations of praseodymium ion in mixtures containing various cations. Table 3 indicates that the ac-

Table 3. Determination of Pr³⁺ ion in presence of metal ions mixture

Pr ³⁺ (mol L ⁻¹)	Added cations (mol L ⁻¹)	Found ^a (mol L ⁻¹)	Recovery (%)
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Gd(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Lu(NO ₃) ₃	1.04×10^{-8}	104
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Eu(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Er(NO ₃) ₃	1.03×10^{-8}	103
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)La(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Ho(NO ₃) ₃	1.04×10^{-8}	104
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Dy(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Yb(NO ₃) ₃	1.02×10^{-8}	102
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Tb(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Nd(NO ₃) ₃	1.02×10^{-8}	102
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Na(NO ₃) and (0.00001)Ca(NO ₃) ₂	1.03×10^{-8}	103
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Pb(NO ₃) ₂ and (0.00001)Ni(NO ₃) ₂	1.02×10^{-8}	102
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Cr(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Fe(NO ₃) ₃	1.01×10^{-8}	101
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)K(NO ₃) and (0.00001)Mg(NO ₃) ₂	1.01×10^{-8}	101
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Pb(NO ₃) ₂ and (0.00001)Ca(NO ₃) ₂ and (0.00001)K(NO ₃)	1.02×10^{-8}	102
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Pb(NO ₃) ₂ and (0.00001)Na(NO ₃) and (0.00001)Ca(NO ₃) ₂	1.00×10^{-8}	100

^aResults are based on three measurements.

Fig. 6. Titration curves of Pr³⁺ solution (25 mL 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹) with EDTA (1.0 × 10⁻² mol L⁻¹).

curacy of the Pr³⁺ ions detection in different solutions of different metal ions is almost quantitative.

Conclusion

In present work, STCH was put to use as a sensing material due to trend of it to form complexation with Pr³⁺ ions in create of new PrCPE. The best composition for the Pr³⁺ electrode was STCH : 3%, paraffin oil : 30%, MWCNT : 2%, NS : 0.3%, and graphite powder : 64.7%. This sensor illustrated the Nernstian behavior with the slope of 19.6 ± 0.2 mV per decade over the widish linear range of 1.0 × 10⁻⁸ to 1.0 × 10⁻² mol L⁻¹ and the detection limit about 8.5 × 10⁻⁹ mol L⁻¹. In pH range of 2.1–8.9 this electrode work independently toward the changes of H₃O⁺ ions activity.

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